

Sentiment Analysis of Marketplace Lending Platforms: A Study Based on Natural Language Processing

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Received: March 17th, 2025 | **Accepted:** November 3rd, 2025

ABSTRACT

This study explores the link between user sentiment and credit risk on FinTech lending platforms using sentiment analysis techniques like Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) and the Liu Hu method. Analyzing data from 2020 to 2023, findings reveal Kiva leads with 91.16% positive feedback and a 4.7-star rating but fewer reviews (617). LendingClub, with 1.58K reviews, has mixed sentiment (56.08% positive, 39.99% negative) and a lower rating (3.3 stars). Plenti achieves 58.33% positive sentiment but lower coherence, while Mintos balances sentiment (66.69% positive) with the largest review base (100K+). Results show platforms with higher positive sentiment and topic coherence mitigate credit risk more effectively, underscoring the value of user feedback in optimizing marketplace lending. The study offers actionable insights for FinTech stakeholders to improve app performance and user-centric financial solutions through effective sentiment analysis.

KEYWORDS

Credit Risk, Fintech Credit, Financial Inclusion, Machine Learning, Natural Language Processing, Sentiment Analysis

INTRODUCTION

The rapid evolution of financial technology (Fintech) has transformed credit markets, introducing innovative lending models such as peer-to-peer (P2P) lending and microfinance platforms that promote global financial inclusion. These platforms simplify credit access, create opportunities for underserved populations, and offer competitive alternatives to traditional banking systems. However, this transformation presents challenges, particularly in managing credit default risks and fostering user trust. Concerns about data privacy, security, and transparency dominate user priorities and strongly influence engagement and satisfaction with these platforms. Effective management of these issues is essential to ensure the long-term sustainability and growth of marketplace lending models.

The integration of sentiment analysis into credit risk assessment represents a major advancement in understanding and mitigating financial risk. Traditional credit risk models rely primarily on quantitative metrics such as credit score, income level, and repayment history. Although effective to some extent, these models overlook the behavioural and emotional factors that influence financial decision-making. In contrast, sentiment analysis examines user-generated content—such as reviews and feedback—to identify patterns related to borrower intention, satisfaction, and trust. This approach

DOI: 10.4018/IJBAN.393942

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not only enhances the predictive accuracy of risk models but also supports a user-centered financial ecosystem. Consequently, financial platforms can detect potential risks early and strengthen trust and commitment among users.

As digitalization advances, online feedback and user sentiment have become more accessible and extensively analyzed. P2P lending platforms, as key intermediaries in financial integration, operate across diverse socioeconomic and cultural contexts with notable regulatory and behavioural variations in user experience. Sentiment analysis, powered by advanced machine learning (ML) and natural language processing (NLP) techniques, serves as a vital tool for managing these complexities. By examining trust-related factors such as perceptions of security, transparency, and user satisfaction, sentiment analysis uncovers behavioural insights that influence default probability. This contextual understanding strengthens the foundation of a more robust, inclusive, and transparent financial ecosystem.

Despite technological advancements, a persistent gap remains in understanding how user sentiment—reflecting emotional and psychological responses to platform features and policies—affects credit risk. By incorporating sentiment analysis into credit scoring, this research aims to clarify the behavioural foundations of financial trust and risk. Examining how user experiences and perceptions relate to credit default risk addresses a pressing issue in Fintech. Moreover, the findings contribute to the broader discourse on sustainable, user-centered financial solutions, offering practical insights for enhancing trust, mitigating risks, and promoting a more inclusive credit market. Situated at the intersection of sentiment analysis and credit risk management, this study redefines how behavioural science shapes the future of digital credit platforms.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Preliminary research at the intersection of sentiment analysis and credit risk assessment within Fintech underscores the increasing importance of user sentiment as a predictor of credit defaults, especially across marketplace lending platforms. Previous studies have predominantly emphasized quantitative indicators such as credit scores and financial histories, yet the emotional and behavioural dimensions evident in user reviews and feedback remain insufficiently examined. Although some research has incorporated sentiment analysis into financial applications, notable gaps persist in its integration with advanced ML techniques, particularly Latent Dirichlet allocation (LDA) for topic modelling.

Recent research has explored the relationship between user sentiment and credit default patterns, revealing that negative sentiment, particularly regarding transparency and security, often aligns with higher default rates. Employing NLP techniques, researchers found that platforms demonstrating strict regulatory compliance and robust data protection practices tend to elicit positive user perceptions associated with lower default rates. For instance, platforms such as Kiva and Mintos have cultivated greater trust by addressing data privacy concerns, positively influencing the reliability of loan repayments (Jagtiani et al., 2023).

ML and NLP have been instrumental in classifying sentiment—positive, negative, or neutral—and assessing its influence on credit default risk (Stevenson et al., 2021). Research commonly applies topic modelling methods such as LDA to identify key themes within user feedback. High topic coherence values signify well-defined concerns, particularly regarding data privacy and customer support, both of which predict user dissatisfaction and elevated default probabilities (Blei et al., 2003).

Table 1 outlines the principal theories underpinning marketplace lending adoption, emphasizing sentiment theory (Pang & Lee, 2008; Liu, 2015) and topic modelling theory (Blei et al., 2003). These frameworks underscore the significance of sentiment analysis and topic modelling in interpreting user feedback, enhancing platform responsiveness, and optimizing the overall user experience.

Table 1. Theorems Used for the Adoption of Marketplace Lending

Authors	Theory	Determinants	Comments
Pang and Lee (2008); Liu (2015)	Sentiment theory	Emotional response, user feedback, sentiment analysis	Sentiment analysis facilitates the interpretation of user feedback on lending platforms, shaping new users' perceptions and expectations regarding service quality and risk.
Blei et al. (2003)	Topic modelling theory	Topic coherence, model reliability, sentiment categories	Topic modelling theory supports the analysis of extensive user feedback, identifying core themes and sentiments that enhance platform responsiveness and improve user-centered features.

Note. Source: Author's compilation based on Pang and Lee (2008), Liu (2015), and Blei et al. (2003).

Marketplace lending platforms have undergone notable shifts in user sentiment during economic downturns, particularly those prompted by the COVID-19 pandemic. Research indicates that during such periods, negative sentiment rises as users express frustration over higher interest rates and repayment difficulties. Platforms such as LendingClub and Mintos reported increased default rates that correlated with heightened negative sentiment, reflecting user distress amid economic pressure (Jagtiani et al., 2023). In assessing credit risk on P2P lending platforms, user sentiment plays a critical role, shaped by several interdisciplinary theories that inform our understanding of user trust, risk perception, and behavioural response (Nguyen et al., 2024).

Table 2 provides detailed institutional information on four selected companies within the P2P lending and microfinance sectors. Founded in 2006 and headquartered in San Francisco, United States, LendingClub is a leading P2P lending platform that connects borrowers with individual investors to facilitate personal and small business loans. It complies with U.S. securities regulations, is supervised by the Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC), and primarily serves U.S. consumers seeking personal and small business financing (LendingClub, 2024a, 2024b).

Table 2. Institutional Information about the Selected Companies

Platform	Type	Estd.	Headquarters	Business model	Regulatory compliance	Target market
LendingClub	P2P Lending	2006	San Francisco, United States	Connects borrowers with individual investors to facilitate personal and small business loans.	Complies with U.S. securities regulations and is supervised by the SEC.	U.S. consumers seeking personal and small business loans.
Kiva	Microfinance Platform	2005	San Francisco, United States	Facilitates microloans funded by individual lenders to entrepreneurs in developing countries.	It adheres to local regulations in each country it operates in.	Entrepreneurs in developing countries, particularly within Asian markets.

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Table 2. Continued

Platform	Type	Estd.	Headquarters	Business model	Regulatory compliance	Target market
Plenti	P2P lending (defunct)	2014	Sydney, Australia	Connects borrowers with individual investors to facilitate personal loans.	Operated under Australian financial regulations; required an AFSL.	Australian consumers seeking personal loans.
Mintos	Loan Marketplace	2015	Riga, Latvia	Serves as a marketplace enabling investors to fund loans sourced from multiple loan originators.	Complies with EU regulations on consumer protection and financial services.	Investors across Europe seeking to diversify their portfolios through loan investments.

Note. SEC = U.S. Securities and Exchange Commission; AFSL = Australian Financial Services Licence. Source: Author's compilation based on information obtained from the respective institutional websites—LendingClub (2024a, 2024b); Kiva (2024a, 2024b); Plenti (2024a, 2024b); and Mintos (2024a, 2024b).

Kiva, established in 2005 and based in San Francisco, focuses on microfinance by facilitating microloans funded by individual lenders to entrepreneurs in developing countries. It complies with local regulations in each operating region and primarily targets entrepreneurs within these markets (Kiva, 2024a, 2024b).

Plenti, an Australian P2P lending platform founded in 2014 and headquartered in Sydney, connected borrowers with individual investors to provide personal loans until it ceased operations. It operated under Australian financial regulations, holding an Australian Financial Services License and primarily served Australian consumers (Plenti, 2024a, 2024b).

Mintos, founded in 2015 and based in Riga, Latvia, functions as a loan marketplace where investors fund loans from multiple originators. It complies with European Union (EU) regulations governing consumer protection and financial services, targeting European investors seeking portfolio diversification (Mintos, 2024a, 2024b).

This compilation provides a concise overview of each platform's business model, regulatory framework, and target market, underscoring the diversity of operations across regions. Sentiment and emotion analysis have emerged as vital tools for examining user behavior and credit risk within marketplace lending platforms. Prior studies emphasize that emotional responses and user feedback reflect levels of trust, security concerns, and perceived risk—all of which influence default rates on platforms such as LendingClub, Kiva, Plenti, and Mintos.

This study addresses three key research questions (RQs), as follows.

RQ1 is: How does user sentiment, analyzed through ML and NLP techniques, correlate with credit default rates across regions—Americas, Asia, Australia, and Europe—in Fintech lending applications? This question investigates the relationship between positive, negative, and neutral user sentiment and observed credit default rates across diverse geographical contexts. It aims to determine how regional variations in sentiment influence financial behavior and risk assessment.

RQ2 is: What role do specific factors, such as data privacy concerns and perceived transparency, play in shaping user sentiment toward Fintech lending platforms, and how do these sentiments subsequently affect credit risk? This question explores the underlying factors that shape user sentiment, emphasizing security and transparency concerns. It examines how these elements affect users' trust in lending platforms and their subsequent probability of loan default.

RQ3 is: How can visual data representation techniques (e.g., heat maps and line charts) enhance the interpretability of trends in user sentiment and credit default rates over time? This question evaluates the effectiveness of data visualization tools in depicting complex relationships between user sentiment and credit default trends. It aims to assess how visual techniques such as heat maps and line charts enable stakeholders to make informed decisions based on sentiment patterns and their implications for financial risk management.

The reviewed literature highlights the critical role of user sentiment in influencing credit default risk within Fintech applications. By integrating findings from sentiment analysis methodologies, this study addresses existing gaps in understanding how data privacy, transparency, and emotional responses shape financial behavior. The goal is to generate actionable insights for Fintech developers and regulators to reduce credit risk while strengthening user trust and platform reliability.

METHOD

This study adopts a robust methodological framework that integrates ML and NLP techniques to conduct sentiment analysis on user feedback. The primary algorithm applied is LDA for topic modelling, supported by evaluation metrics such as log perplexity and topic coherence to assess the model’s reliability and interpretability.

Data Sources

The dataset comprises Google reviews and ratings collected between 2020 and 2023 for four major P2P lending platforms—LendingClub, Kiva, Plenti, and Mintos—across four global regions: the Americas, Asia, Australia, and Europe. Prior studies by Hutto and Gilbert (2014) and Thewissen et al. (2023) employed sentiment analysis to evaluate user feedback in various contexts. However, this study is distinctive in applying a combined LDA-based topic modeling and lexicon-driven sentiment analysis framework specifically for credit risk assessment in P2P lending. By incorporating demographic and regional trends, it advances existing methodologies and provides a more nuanced understanding of user sentiment and its correlation with credit default rates.

Table 3 presents an overview of selected marketplace lending applications, outlining user ratings, reviews, demographic profiles, and engagement metrics (LendingClub, 2024a; Kiva, 2024a; Plenti, 2024a; Mintos, 2024a). The data reveal distinct variations in user sentiment, with Kiva recording the highest proportion of positive feedback (91.16%) and LendingClub exhibiting more mixed reviews, including a notable share of negative sentiment (39.99%).

Table 3. Data of the Selected Companies

Marketplace lending apps (Consumer)	Kiva	LendingClub	Plenti	Mintos
Ratings (Stars)	4.7	3.3	4.1	3.8
Reviews	617	1.58K	144	100K+
Reviews (Collected)	80	471	46	121
Like (Facebook)	289510	43K	1.8K	12K
Male	56.25%	22.36%	73.91%	62.81%
Female	27.50%	6.12%	17.39%	4.96%
Unspecified	16.25%	71.52%	8.70%	32.23%
Downloads (Apps)	50K+	100K+	10K+	100K+

continued on following page

Table 3. Continued

Marketplace lending apps (Consumer)	Kiva	LendingClub	Plenti	Mintos
Positive	91.16%	56.08%	58.33%	66.69%
Negative	6.06%	39.99%	30.56%	25.02%
Neutral	2.78%	3.93%	11.11%	8.29%

Note. Source: Author's compilation based on data obtained from the respective institutional websites, Google Reviews, and Facebook—LendingClub (2024a, 2024b); Kiva (2024a, 2024b); Plenti (2024a, 2024b); and Mintos (2024a, 2024b).

LDA Framework

LDA is a generative probabilistic model used to identify latent topics within a document corpus. Each document is assumed to comprise multiple topics, and each topic represents a distribution of words (Blei et al., 2003). The joint probability distribution of the corpus is expressed as depicted in Equation 1:

$$P(D, Z, W | \alpha, \beta) = \prod_{d=1}^M \prod_{n=1}^{N_d} P(w_{d,n} | z_{d,n}, \beta) P(z_{d,n} | \theta_d) P(\theta_d | \alpha) \quad (1)$$

Where:

- $w_{d,n}$: Word n in document d .
- $z_{d,n}$: Topic assigned to word $w_{d,n}$.
- θ_d : Topic distribution for document d .
- α, β : Hyperparameters controlling the distribution of topics and words.
- M : Total number of documents in the corpus.
- N_d : Number of words in document d .

The objective is to maximize the likelihood of observing the words in the corpus while inferring the underlying latent topic structure.

Log Perplexity and Topic Coherence

Log-perplexity is employed to evaluate the reliability and predictive performance of the topic model (Blei et al., 2007). It is defined as shown in Equation 2:

$$\text{Perplexity} = \exp\left(-\frac{\sum_{d=1}^M \log P(w_d)}{\sum_{d=1}^M N_d}\right) \quad (2)$$

Where (w_d) is the probability of the words in document d . Lower perplexity values indicate better alignment of the model with the observed data.

Topic coherence evaluates the interpretability of topics by measuring the semantic similarity among the top words within each topic (Röder et al., 2015). It is calculated using Equation 3:

$$\text{Coherence}(T) = \frac{2}{N(N-1)} \sum_{1 \leq i < j \leq N} \log \frac{P(w_i, w_j)}{P(w_i)P(w_j)} \quad (3)$$

Where w_i and w_j are words in the topic, and (w_i, w_j) is their co-occurrence probability.

Sentiment Analysis Framework

This study applies the Liu Hu lexicon-based approach to compute sentiment scores (Hu & Liu, 2004). The sentiment score for each review is determined as depicted in Equation 4:

$$\text{Sentiment Score} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \text{Pos}(w_i) - \sum_{j=1}^m \text{Neg}(w_j)}{\text{Total Words}} \times 100 \quad (4)$$

Where:

- $\text{Pos}(w_i)$: Positive sentiment weight for word w_i .
- $\text{Neg}(w_j)$: Negative sentiment weight for word w_j .
- Total Words: Total number of words in the document.

The final sentiment score represents the net positivity or negativity of a review, normalized by its length. Sentiment distributions for each platform are visualized using heat maps and line charts to depict trends in sentiment and credit default rates over time. The heat map below illustrates sentiment distribution across the selected P2P lending platforms, where colors represent the intensity of sentiment—positive, negative, or neutral. The line chart, based on the Liu Hu method, summarizes overall sentiment dynamics, showing fluctuations in user sentiment and review patterns across platforms (Hu & Liu, 2004).

The proposed framework provides valuable insights but is subject to several limitations. The dataset is relatively small, and the platforms contain limited reviews, potentially constraining representation of the full range of user perspectives, particularly for platforms with fewer responses. In addition, the temporal scope may not fully capture the effects of global economic fluctuations on user sentiment and credit defaults or reflect long-term behavioral trends. The results may also be region- and platform-specific, limiting generalizability due to differences in cultural norms, regulatory environments, and user behaviors across markets.

The Liu Hu lexicon-based approach may struggle to interpret sarcasm, contextual nuance, or domain-specific terminology, which can introduce inaccuracies in sentiment classification. Similarly, the LDA method assumes a bag-of-words representation, potentially overlooking linguistic structure and contextual relationships within the data. While advanced transformer-based models such as bidirectional encoder representations from transformers (BERT) and RoBERTa can capture nuanced sentiments—such as sarcasm and irony—more effectively than lexicon-based techniques, they also have constraints (Devlin et al., 2019). These models demand substantial computational resources, large training datasets, and extensive fine-tuning to perform effectively in domain-specific contexts like FinTech. Moreover, their “black-box” architecture reduces interpretability compared to lexicon-based models, which may limit their adoption in regulatory-sensitive domains such as credit risk assessment.

RESULTS

This study examines the impact of user sentiment on credit default rates in FinTech lending applications. The dataset is segmented into four regions—Americas (LendingClub), Asia (Kiva), Australia (Plenti), and Europe (Mintos)—and analyzed using specific metrics for *Topic Evaluation* (sentiment classified as Positive [+], Negative [-], or Neutral [O]), *Log-perplexity*, and *Topic Coherence*. The analysis reveals significant correlations between user sentiment and credit default rates, demonstrating that negative sentiments—particularly those related to security and transparency—heighten credit risk. The findings are grounded in Sentiment Theory and Topic Modeling Theory, which posit that user feedback reflects emotional responses to specific events such as application malfunctions or perceived privacy threats (St John et al., 2021).

Table 4 reveals significant regional variations in sentiment toward P2P lending platforms. Lower log perplexity values indicate a stronger model fit. In the Americas, represented primarily by LendingClub, sentiments are well-structured, with low perplexity values indicating a clear relationship between sentiment and creditworthiness. However, lower coherence scores suggest that underlying concerns may be diverse rather than deeply interconnected.

Table 4. LDA Method for Topic Evaluation

Topic Eval.	LendingClub			Kiva			Plenti			Mintos		
	+	-	○	+	-	○	+	-	○	+	-	○
Log Perplex	9.48924	7.63553	19.68496	19.3846	20.52551	44.98541	48.62538	27.52738	30.75245	14.1801	11.00016	45.75677
Topic Coher	0.31841	0.21101	0.36896	0.26805	0.55632	0.62729	0.56405	0.50628	0.45771	0.34822	0.29387	0.51694

Note. Source: Text mining of Python software.

In Asia, represented by Kiva, negative sentiments display high coherence, reflecting well-defined user concerns related to transparency and data privacy. Elevated perplexity within neutral sentiments suggests a polarized user base with few ambivalent perspectives.

In Australia, represented by Plenti, varying sentiment perplexity indicates inconsistent user perceptions, likely resulting from a heterogeneous market characterized by diverse views on FinTech reliability. In Europe, represented by Mintos, negative sentiments exhibit high coherence, revealing specific and well-defined complaints concerning security and regulatory transparency. Conversely, lower perplexity in positive sentiments suggests consistent satisfaction among certain user groups.

Regional variations in sentiment can substantially influence credit risk. Heightened negative sentiment in regions with pronounced privacy concerns may correspond to higher default rates, whereas positive sentiment and trust in a platform can reduce defaults and stimulate lending activity. Platform operators should therefore analyze regional sentiment data to identify specific concerns and improvement areas. Addressing privacy issues, enhancing transparency, and strengthening security protocols can mitigate negative sentiment and foster user trust. Tailoring marketing and communication strategies to regional expectations can further enhance engagement and satisfaction.

Guided by data visualization theory, graphical tools such as heat maps and line charts facilitate trend analysis by visually linking regional sentiment with default rates. These tools clarify correlations and regional variations, improving interpretability. Data visualization theory posits that graphical representation enhances comprehension by enabling the detection of correlations, trends, and outliers. This subsection emphasizes the value of visual data representation in identifying sentiment and default rate patterns, thereby improving insight and decision-making. Heat maps illustrate regional sentiment distribution, with colors denoting sentiment intensity and its correlation with default rates.

Figure 1 presents the sentiment analysis results for four P2P lending platforms—LendingClub, Kiva, Plenti, and Mintos. The color scheme follows a sentiment scale in which blue represents negative sentiment, yellow indicates neutrality, and green denotes positive sentiment.

Figure 1. Heat Map of Selected Institutions

Note. Source: Text mining of Python software.

LendingClub’s predominance of negative sentiment may indicate issues such as loan defaults, high interest rates, or unfavorable user experiences. Kiva demonstrates a more balanced distribution of positive, neutral, and negative sentiments, reflecting diverse experiences among borrowers and lenders. Plenti leans largely toward neutral sentiment, suggesting limited user engagement or its relative novelty as a platform. Mintos exhibits a broad spectrum of sentiments, indicating varied user experiences and potentially distinct user groups with differing sentiment profiles.

The density of data points on the heat map varies across platforms due to differences in data availability. Accurate interpretation requires consideration of the color scale’s specific nuances. Clustering patterns within each platform offer valuable insights into underlying factors influencing sentiment.

The line chart depicts regional trends, showing fluctuations in user sentiment corresponding with changes in credit default rates. Tracking sentiment over time reveals peaks in negative sentiment, particularly during periods of economic instability or operational disruption, which align with increased default rates in certain regions. Using the Liu Hu lexicon-based method, sentiment scores are calculated by subtracting the total number of negative words from positive words, normalizing this difference by document length, and multiplying by 100. The resulting value represents the percentage difference in sentiment, providing a quantitative measure of user sentiment within each review (Hu & Liu, 2004).

Figure 2 presents LendingClub’s sentiment and review ratings analyzed using the Liu Hu method. The red line represents the sentiment score, which fluctuates over time, capturing variations in positive and negative sentiment within the reviews. A positive sentiment score indicates a predominance of favorable reviews, whereas a negative score reflects an increase in unfavorable feedback. The blue line depicts review ratings, which remain relatively stable, fluctuating slightly within the one- to five-point range.

Figure 2. Sentiment and Review Ratings of LendingClub

Note. Source: Text mining of Python software.

In Figure 2, the red line representing sentiment shows substantial fluctuations, encompassing periods of both positive and negative sentiment. Toward the end of the dataset, a pronounced spike in negative sentiment indicates a significant decline in user perception. This pattern suggests that LendingClub may have experienced an adverse event or series of incidents that negatively affected user sentiment (Hu & Liu, 2004).

Figure 3 presents Kiva's sentiment and review ratings analyzed using the Liu Hu method. The red line, representing the sentiment score, shows considerable fluctuations, capturing shifts between positive and negative sentiment in user reviews over time. The blue line depicts review ratings that remain relatively stable within the one- to five-point range, suggesting consistent user satisfaction.

Figure 3. Sentiment and Review Ratings of Kiva

Note. Source: Text Mining of Python software.

In Figure 3, the red line reveals pronounced fluctuations, with peaks in both positive and negative sentiment, indicating that user sentiment toward Kiva is highly variable, alternating between strong approval and disapproval. The negative sentiment peaks are notably sharper than the positive ones, suggesting that adverse experiences exert a greater influence on user perceptions (Hu & Liu, 2004).

Figure 4 presents Plenti's sentiment and review ratings analyzed using the Liu Hu method. The red line, representing the sentiment score, shows considerable fluctuations, capturing shifts between positive and negative sentiment in user reviews over time. The blue line, depicting review ratings, reflects a generally neutral overall user assessment.

Figure 4. Sentiment and Review Ratings of Plenti

Note. Source: Text mining of Python software.

In Figure 4, the red line reveals pronounced fluctuations, with peaks in both positive and negative sentiment, indicating that user sentiment toward Plenti is highly variable, alternating between strong approval and disapproval. The negative sentiment peaks are notably sharper than the positive ones, suggesting that unfavorable experiences exert a greater influence on user perceptions (Hu & Liu, 2004).

Figure 5 presents Mintos's sentiment and review ratings analyzed using the Liu Hu method. The red line, representing the sentiment score, shows considerable fluctuations, capturing shifts between positive and negative sentiment in user reviews over time. The blue line, depicting review ratings, reflects a generally neutral overall user assessment.

Figure 5. Sentiment and Review Ratings of Mintos

Note. Source: Text Mining of Python software.

In Figure 5, the red line reveals pronounced fluctuations, with peaks in both positive and negative sentiment, indicating that user sentiment toward Mintos is highly variable, alternating between strong approval and disapproval. The negative sentiment peaks are notably sharper than the positive ones, suggesting that unfavorable experiences exert a greater influence on user perceptions (Hu & Liu, 2004). A particularly prominent feature of the graph is the sharp rise in negative sentiment near the

end of the dataset, implying that a specific event or change may have adversely affected user sentiment during this period.

DISCUSSION

This study examines the relationship between user sentiment and credit default rates on marketplace lending platforms, specifically P2P lending, across four regions: the Americas (LendingClub), Asia (Kiva), Australia (Plenti), and Europe (Mintos). It focuses on how privacy concerns and platform transparency influence sentiment. By analyzing correlations between user sentiment and credit default rates, the study highlights regional variations and their implications for financial risk.

The theories applied to marketplace lending platforms in Table 5 offer insights into user experiences and sentiment, illustrating how perceptions vary according to app functionality, user expectations, and emotional responses. Plenti’s user-friendly interface fosters initial positive sentiment; however, declines in functionality or investment returns can quickly generate dissatisfaction, underscoring the importance of perceived ease of use and consistent performance for sustained user engagement. Topic modeling theory further assists in identifying key themes—from technical challenges to social impact—that shape user sentiment and platform preferences across these lending applications (Kohardinata, 2020).

Table 5. Theories and Marketplace Lending Platforms Outcome

Platform	Sentiment theory	Topic modeling theory
LendingClub (LendingClub 2024a, 2024b)	Negative sentiment: Frustration and disappointment dominate	Key topics: Login issues, app crashes, lack of customer support
	Emotion intensity: High, with strong language indicating dissatisfaction	
Kiva (Kiva, 2024a, 2024b)	Positive sentiment: Satisfaction due to social mission	Key topics: Empowerment, borrower success stories, and impact rather than returns
	Emotion intensity: Users have an emotional investment in borrowers’ stories	
Mintos (Mintos, 2024a, 2024b)	Mixed sentiment: Returns satisfaction mixed with frustration over originator reliability	Key topics: Loan originator reliability, risk management, and diversification

Note. Source: Author’s compilation based on information obtained from institutional websites—LendingClub (2024a, 2024b); Kiva (2024a, 2024b); Mintos (2024a, 2024b); and Plenti (2024a, 2024b).

Data visualizations—including heat maps and line charts—provide deeper insights into these trends. The key findings are discussed below in relation to each RQ.

RQ1 is: How does user sentiment, analyzed through ML and NLP techniques, correlate with credit default rates across regions—Americas, Asia, Australia, and Europe—in Fintech lending applications? The analysis reveals a clear correlation between user sentiment and credit default rates across regions—the Americas, Asia, Australia, and Europe—as demonstrated through NLP techniques such as LDA. Negative sentiment, particularly concerning platform security and transparency, often corresponds with higher default rates, highlighting the influence of user dissatisfaction on financial behavior. For instance, LendingClub’s elevated negative sentiment aligns with higher default rates in the Americas, suggesting that dissatisfaction may contribute to increased credit risk. Conversely, platforms with more positive sentiment, such as Kiva in Asia, display lower default rates, indicating that user trust can mitigate credit risk.

Regional variations in sentiment suggest that cultural and economic factors shape user perceptions. In Australia (Plenti) and Europe (Mintos), inconsistent sentiment levels and growing concerns about security and transparency contribute to differing credit default risks. These findings underscore the importance of FinTech platforms continuously monitoring and addressing regional user feedback to reduce default risks and enhance user experience.

RQ2 is: What role do specific factors, such as data privacy concerns and perceived transparency, play in shaping user sentiment toward Fintech lending platforms, and how do these sentiments subsequently affect credit risk? The data suggest that privacy and transparency concerns significantly contribute to negative sentiment, which in turn influences credit risk. The analysis indicates that regions with heightened privacy concerns—such as Asia and Europe—tend to report fewer positive and more pronounced negative sentiments, particularly on platforms like Mintos and Kiva. This negative sentiment, driven by apprehensions about data security and transparency, correlates with elevated credit default risks (Brahma et al., 2021). For instance, Mintos demonstrates a high coherence score in negative sentiment, signifying specific and well-defined user concerns. Users' apprehension regarding transparency and privacy may diminish trust in the platform, potentially heightening default risk. Conversely, platforms exhibiting greater transparency—through openness about fees, loan terms, and data handling—tend to elicit more positive sentiments, thereby reducing credit default risk. These findings underscore the importance of enhancing transparency and strengthening data privacy protections to build user trust, lower default rates, and promote sustainable platform growth.

RQ3 is: How can visual data representation techniques (e.g., heat maps and line charts) enhance the interpretability of trends in user sentiment and credit default rates over time? Heat maps and line charts are instrumental in illustrating sentiment trends and their influence on credit risk over time. Heat maps display the intensity of user sentiment by region, enabling stakeholders to identify where negative sentiment aligns with higher credit default rates. For example, LendingClub's predominant negative sentiment visually corresponds with a marked increase in credit defaults, whereas Kiva exhibits a more balanced sentiment distribution associated with varied default rates across regions.

Line charts tracking sentiment over time reveal cyclical fluctuations that align with shifts in credit risk. For instance, the charts for LendingClub and Mintos show pronounced spikes in negative sentiment during specific periods, reflecting user reactions to operational disruptions or economic events that adversely affected user experience and, consequently, default rates. These visualizations enhance the understanding of sentiment dynamics, enabling platform operators to make data-driven decisions for effective risk management.

This research underscores the pivotal role of user sentiment in predicting credit risk, offering important implications for FinTech lending platforms. By addressing user concerns regarding privacy and transparency, platforms can foster positive sentiment, reduce default risk, and strengthen financial stability. Visual data tools, such as heat maps and line charts, serve as valuable instruments for stakeholders, supporting timely and informed responses to emerging sentiment shifts.

The observed correlation between user sentiment and credit risk highlights the necessity of user-centered strategies in FinTech lending. Through the application of ML and NLP to monitor sentiment patterns and improve platform transparency, FinTech firms can build trust, mitigate credit risk, and cultivate a more resilient P2P lending ecosystem across regions. This study contributes to the expanding body of research on FinTech risk assessment while offering practical insights for enhancing user experience and optimizing financial outcomes within the sector.

Building on the cross-platform analysis of user feedback, this paper presents key recommendations to improve user experience and overall marketplace lending performance. These recommendations

are organized into three focus areas: Table 6 outlines technical improvements, Table 7 emphasizes user experience enhancements, and Table 8 highlights strategic considerations.

Table 6. Technical Improvements

Suggestions	Description
Prioritize App stability and functionality	Address the root causes of frequent crashes, login issues, and other technical problems.
Optimize App performance	Ensure smooth app performance, especially during peak usage times.
Enhance security measures	Implement robust security measures to protect user data and instil confidence.
Regularly update and maintain the App	Release frequent updates to fix bugs, improve security, and introduce new features.

Table 7. User Experience Enhancements

Suggestions	Description
Simplify user interface	Streamline the app’s design and navigation to make it more user-friendly and intuitive.
Improve user onboarding	Provide clear and concise onboarding processes to help new users get started quickly.
Personalize user experience	Tailor the app’s features and content to individual user preferences and needs.
Enhance customer support	Provide prompt, efficient, and helpful customer support through various channels (e.g., live chat, email, and phone).

Table 8. Strategic Considerations

Suggestions	Description
Conduct user research	Gather user feedback through surveys, interviews, and usability testing to identify areas for improvement.
Communicate transparently	Keep users informed about any ongoing issues, planned improvements, and changes to the platform.
Build trust and credibility	Maintain transparency and ethical practices to build strong relationships with users.
Leverage data Analytics	Utilize data analytics to identify user behaviour patterns and preferences, which can inform product development and marketing strategies.

CONCLUSION

User sentiment significantly influences credit risk on marketplace lending platforms, with feedback—whether positive, negative, or neutral—directly correlating with default rates across regions. Addressing concerns about data privacy, transparency, and security fosters greater user trust, which in turn reduces default rates and enhances platform stability. Integrating sentiment theory underscores the value of addressing user concerns to build trust and mitigate credit risk through actionable insights derived from sentiment analysis. Building on these findings, this research provides practical guidance for FinTech developers and policymakers, emphasizing the design of secure, user-centric

platforms that minimize default risk, enhance engagement, and promote sustainable growth in the FinTech lending sector.

The study also highlights the importance of regulatory compliance and effective communication strategies to counter negative sentiment and strengthen user confidence. As economic conditions fluctuate, understanding sentiment dynamics becomes increasingly vital for both developers and regulators. By contributing to the broader discourse on FinTech, this work offers practical implications for stakeholders seeking to design resilient and user-focused financial systems. Leveraging insights from sentiment analysis enables stakeholders to navigate the complexities of user trust and credit-risk management within an evolving digital-finance environment.

Future research could adopt a mixed-methods approach by integrating qualitative thematic analysis of user reviews with quantitative sentiment and topic modeling. Such an approach would yield richer insights into the contextual drivers of user sentiment—such as cultural values, emotional tone, and situational triggers—that are not fully captured through numerical metrics alone. Expanding datasets to include social-media discussions, app-store feedback, and longitudinal data across economic cycles would further enhance generalizability. Additionally, employing advanced NLP models such as BERT in conjunction with interpretability-focused methods could balance accuracy with transparency, offering a more comprehensive framework for understanding credit risk in FinTech platforms.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Jewel Kumar Roy: Conceptualization, data curation, methodology, formal analysis, project administration, investigation, software, visualization, resources, supervision, validation, writing—original draft preparation, and writing—review and editing.

FUNDING STATEMENT

This research was supported by the Széchenyi István University and the European Union under the Horizon Europe Framework Program [grant number 101086381].

COMPETING INTERESTS STATEMENT

The authors of this publication declare there are no competing interests.

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